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India in a Changing Global Order: Geopolitical Challenges and Strategic Interests in the Indo-Myanmar Borderlands

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the borderlands of India and Myanmar as a critical site of India's geopolitical strategy in the context of its Act East Policy and broader regional ambitions. It analyses the complex security challenges arising from cross-border insurgency, narco-trafficking, and China's growing influence in Myanmar, compounded by internal political instability across the border. The study evaluates India's key connectivity initiatives—such as the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project and the India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway—and their role in enhancing regional integration. A balanced approach is emphasised in this paper, which highlights the importance of bilateral cooperation in border management and counterinsurgency. It argues that India must align its security priorities with economic engagement to safeguard its interests and strengthen its strategic presence on the Indo-Myanmar frontier.

Introduction

The India-Myanmar border region has long remained a marginal area in both Indian and global strategic consciousness. Historically, much of what is now recognised as Northeast India remained isolated from the mainstream national narrative, even during the British colonial period. This region, home to a culturally diverse group of ethnic communities, continues to be relatively inaccessible to the broader Indian population. The inner line permit system remains active in most parts of Northeast India, making the region exclusive under constitutional law. Geographically linking India to Myanmar and Southeast Asia, Northeast India has for decades remained, both symbolically and practically, a neglected frontier of the nation. However, in recent years, a change has been underway in New Delhi's approach, with increasing recognition of the region's significance in fostering economic and diplomatic ties with eastern neighbours. The Government of India, under the leadership of Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi, has given its due recognition to Northeast India as not only a strategic bridge to Southeast Asia but also as a key player in regional development initiatives like the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project and the India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway projects. Against this backdrop, the paper analyses the challenges impeding India's regional integration efforts involving the Northeast and Myanmar. The India-Myanmar border is conceptualised here not merely as a physical boundary but as a multidimensional space which encompasses social and cultural exchanges, economic transactions, and zones of both traditional and non-traditional security concerns (Jacob, 2022)

Myanmar holds a significant geopolitical and strategic value for India, serving as a critical link to Southeast Asia. The four northeastern states of India share a 1643-kilometre-long border—

Mizoram (510 km), Nagaland (215 km), Manipur (398 km), Arunachal Pradesh (510 km) (Gupta, 2013). Myanmar's role as a buffer state has gained further significance amid China's increasing presence in Southeast Asia. Considering India's position, Myanmar provides a vital corridor to strengthen its diplomatic, economic and political engagements with both South and Southeast Asia.

The "Look East Policy" launched by the Indian Government in 1991 aimed to strengthen economic and political ties with ASEAN countries following the Cold War. Over time, this policy extended to include nations such as Japan, China and South Korea. In 2014, Prime Minister Narendra Modi introduced the "Act East Policy" and the "Neighbourhood First" policy to accelerate trade relations with neighbouring and regional countries (IAS, 2020). These initiatives are designed to boost India's trade and investment ties across Southeast Asia, the broader Asia-Pacific region, and the Pacific Islands.

Consequently, it becomes imperative for India to deepen its political and economic engagement with Myanmar, not only to safeguard its strategic interest in the high-risk prone Indo-Myanmar borderlands but also to contribute to broader regional stability. Such engagements will be beneficial for India to counterbalance external influences, particularly China's expanding footprint in Myanmar, while fostering cross-border cooperation in areas such as infrastructure development, trade, border security and counter-insurgency. Moreover, sustained diplomatic and developmental collaboration with Myanmar can help address shared challenges like illicit drug trafficking, insurgency financing and population displacement, thereby reinforcing India's position as a strategic and stable power. India is positioned as a responsible regional actor in Southeast Asia.

Research Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research methodology, utilising secondary data sources. The data were drawn from a range of scholarly and public materials, including research articles, academic journals, magazines, newspapers, archival records and relevant online platforms. Additional resources were accessed through various digital and national libraries, such as the Government of India websites, the Embassy of Myanmar, etc. The strategic relevance and geopolitical significance of the India and Myanmar border have been further analysed through careful analysis of different government records, policy documents, etc. Key developmental projects are closely studied and taken into consideration. The secondary data sources provide a broader context and existing knowledge base for analysis. Moreover, this approach enables the researcher to triangulate data, corroborate findings and uncover new insights.

Literature Review

Gupta, R. (2013), in his article on "China, India, Myanmar on strategic perspective", points out the historical marginalisation of India's northeastern region from mainstream peripheral discourses.

The article highlights that India's northeastern states have historically remained disconnected from the strategic and economic mainstream, largely due to colonial-era policies and post-independence neglect, which treated the region as a peripheral frontier rather than an integral part of national development and foreign policy planning.

However, with changing times, the region has assumed considerable influence due to geopolitical dynamics. He also discusses the strategic shift to Myanmar, which is a crucial geopolitical and diplomatic corridor between South Asia and Southeast Asia. Gupta has underscored Myanmar's

importance in India's foreign policy as both a geo-strategic partner and a stabilising influence in the broader Indo-Pacific region.

Ahmad, M (2020), in his article "Bangladesh and the China-India Conflict", talks about the growing vulnerability of the region due to external influences, particularly from China. He lays emphasis on the issue of Indo-China rivalry and border skirmishes in the Ladakh region in the recent decade. Myanmar is viewed with greater significance not only as a transit route for regional cooperation but also as a potential buffer state between competing powers in the geopolitical scenario. The strategic value of Myanmar has also been recognised through institutional mechanisms. Its designation as an observer in the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) in 2008 symbolised a formal acknowledgement of its intermediary role in facilitating regional diplomacy and integration. Accordingly, India's diplomatic outreach to Myanmar is seen as essential for expanding connectivity, enhancing trade, and countering regional security threats, particularly in the context of cross-border insurgencies and narco-trafficking along the Indo-Myanmar borderlands.

In *The India-Myanmar Borderlands: Guns, Blankets and Bird Flu* (2022), Jabin T. Jacob provides a nuanced and interdisciplinary exploration of the India-Myanmar border region, highlighting its significance beyond traditional security discourses. As a working paper published through Hyper articles en ligne (HAL) Open Science, Jacob's study draws attention to the multiple and overlapping dimensions, like political, economic, social and public health-related, that characterise the borderlands. Moving away from narrow state-centric frameworks, the author interrogates how everyday life in these peripheral spaces is shaped by transnational networks, informal economies, and the limited yet strategic presence of the state. Jacob has situated the Indo-Myanmar border not merely as a security frontier but as a lived space where borders are simultaneously porous and policed for law-and-order maintenance. He investigates the proliferation of arms trafficking ("guns"), development aid ("blankets") and zoonotic disease surveillance ("bird flu") intersect in producing the logic of governance and neglect in the region. By focusing on these three symbolic markers, the study reflects on the broader marginalisation of the Northeast in Indian policymaking while also critiquing the ad hoc and reactive nature of Indian state intervention in the borderlands.

The 2023 report by the *United Nations Special Rapporteur on the Situation of Human Rights in Myanmar* (17 May 2023) presents a stark and urgent overview of the deepening humanitarian and political crisis in Myanmar following the military coup of February 2021. The report examines the intensification of the conflict between the State Administrative Council (SAC) and the junta with various resistance groups, resulting in widespread human rights violations, including the targeting of civilian facilities, detentions in an arbitrary manner and indiscriminate airstrikes. The report highlights the junta's reliance on foreign military support, which has prolonged its capacity for violence and repression. Crucially, the report identifies the role of foreign arms suppliers, particularly from China and Russia, in sustaining the junta's military operations. It documents that 41 Chinese and Hong Kong-based private and state-owned entities have supplied the Tatmadaw with significant military hardware between October 2021 and December 2022, including fighter jet components, trainer aircraft and upgraded armaments.

This theme is echoed and deepened in Nicola Smith's article in *The Telegraph* (23 November 2023), which investigates the evolving posture of China toward Myanmar's internal conflict. At the same time, Beijing has historically maintained strategic ties with the Tatmadaw for geopolitical leverage and access to the natural resources of Myanmar. Smith reports a growing Chinese unease which stems not only from criminal syndicates operating online scams from Myanmar's territory, targeting Chinese nationals, but also from human trafficking. These developments, coupled with regional insecurity, may have prompted the Chinese to shift their calculus, giving what Smith terms a "tacit blessing" to the resistance movement's offensive against the junta. Smith's account reveals a geopolitical reconfiguration where Chinese support for the SAC appears conditional and increasingly

transactional. There is a complex triadic relationship between the Tatmadaw, armed resistance groups and the People's Republic of China (PRC). Beijing denies in its official stance any interference; however, there is every possibility of Chinese-backed anti-junta forces in Myanmar's conflict. Bhaumik (2022), in his analysis of India's strategic engagement with Myanmar in his article "Irrawaddy Imperatives: Reviewing India's Myanmar Strategy", underscores that political stability and cooperative governance in Myanmar are essential for the success of India's Act East Policy. He argues that Myanmar's internal peace directly affects both the security environment and developmental prospects of Northeast India, thereby facilitating strong bilateral ties to foster regional stability and economic growth.

Recent scholarship gives a critical examination of the limitations and strategic implications of India's engagement with Myanmar under its *Look East* and *Act East* policies. Singh (2023), in his study *Borderland Realities: Decoding the Socioeconomic and Political Complexities of the Indo-Myanmar Border*, argues that these policy frameworks have not been able to come up with the desired outcomes in terms of economic and security benefits for Northeast India. Singh emphasises the need for multidimensional and locally grounded interventions to address the persistent structural and geopolitical complexities that define the Indo-Myanmar border.

Building on this discourse, Latt (2023), in *India's Act East Policy and Neighbouring Powers: India-Myanmar Relations*, highlights that robust India-Myanmar relations are essential to ensuring regional stability and growth. His analysis lays emphasis on the significance of building cultural linkages, economic cooperation, and strategic partnerships, especially as countermeasures to China's expanding influence in Southeast Asia.

Similarly, Dubey (2024), in *Strategic Dynamics of India-Myanmar Relations: An Assessment*, asserts that the evolving geopolitical landscape and ongoing instability in Myanmar pose significant challenges to the successful implementation of India's Act East Policy. He stressed that India's northeastern frontier can be safeguarded by strengthening border security, and a recalibration of India's strategic approach is needed to secure the demographic integrity.

Theoretical Background

This study is grounded in a realist geopolitical framework, which views states as rational actors navigating a competitive international system to maximise security and power for national interest. The Indo-Myanmar borderlands, situated at the intersection of competing national interests, illustrate the realist logic of balancing threats and securing borders amid rising pressure from external forces like China. There are strategic responses from the Indian side, like infrastructure development and military position in the region, which address the vulnerabilities and evolving power dynamics in its neighbourhood.

Simultaneously, the paper draws upon critical geopolitics, which interrogates how state actors construct spatial narratives such as the "Act East Policy" to assert influence and territorial control. The borderlands are not passive peripheries but active geopolitical zones, which are shaped by narratives of connectivity, security and sovereignty. This theoretical lens helps unpack the material and symbolic significance India attaches to the region in its effort to realign itself in the Indo-Pacific order.

From the perspective of regional integration and complex interdependence (Keohane and Nye, 1977), this paper is an exploration of how trade, infrastructure and diplomatic linkages create overlapping spheres of cooperation and competition. Large-scale initiatives such as the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project and the India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway reflect India's

strategic intent to integrate the Northeastern region into broader regional architectures, while simultaneously reducing vulnerabilities related to dependency and insecurity.

(Donnan and Wilson, 1999) in *Borders: Frontiers of identity, nation and state* discusses how borders are socially constructed and experienced, emphasizing the cultural, economic and political dynamics that unfold in borderlands. The research is informed by borderland studies, particularly the idea of borders as zones of negotiation rather than fixed lines. The Indo-Myanmar frontier is marked by porousness, ethnic ties, illicit flows (e.g narcotics and arms) and insurgent mobility, all of which act as a detriment for the traditional Westphalian notion of sovereignty and territoriality. This approach highlights the agency of local actors and the fluid nature of governance in such contested spaces.

By integrating these theoretical approaches, the paper situates India's policy and strategic behaviour within the fold of the structure of the global political arena and border governance. This shall allow for a nuanced understanding of the opportunities and detrimental factors that define the Indo-Myanmar borderlands. This research draws on borderland studies to explore how borders are not merely fixed territorial demarcations but are socially constructed and lived spaces shaped by cultural, economic, and political interactions. It points to the understanding of borders as a zone of negotiation and fluid exchange rather than rigid lines. The Indo-Myanmar frontier exemplifies this perspective, characterised by its porous nature, strong cross-border ethnic affiliations, the movement of illicit goods such as narcotics and arms, and the mobility of insurgent groups like the NSCN-K, all of which are a challenge to the conventional Westphalian notion of state sovereignty and territorial control.

The paper also takes Territoriality as a conceptual base to understand the efforts made by individuals or groups to shape, influence or dominate people, events, and interactions by defining and claiming authority over a specific geographical space (Sack, 1986). It functions as a spatial tactic where boundaries and territory are employed to regulate, organise and convey power dynamics—ranging from peaceful and cooperative methods to aggressive and coercive forms (Anderson, 2002)

Considering the postcolonial contexts, the demarcation of national borders was arbitrarily conducted by colonial powers, often giving little consideration to the ethnic, linguistic, or cultural continuities of the populations affected (Anderson and O' Dowd, 1999; Donnan and Wilson, 1999). These hastily demarcated boundaries not only divided long-established communities but, in some cases, split individual households between two sovereign territories. In such borderlands, the histories of migration and cross-border interaction supersede the establishment of modern states, and the question of citizenship often becomes a deeply contested issue in postcolonial political discourse (Van Schendel, 2005).

Border crossing in these regions is frequently a part of everyday life, motivated by factors such as infrastructural deficiencies, subsistence livelihood, and familial connections on both sides of the divide (Cons, 2016). Furthermore, ethnic and political conflicts have transformed several border regions into zones of refuge, as individuals and communities from different ethnicities seek refuge from violence, displacement or state-sponsored violence and atrocities (Zolberg et al., 1989). When such movements in many regions of the world, particularly the border regions, are occurring outside legal frameworks, they remain undocumented and unrecognised. Individuals have to face social exclusion, ethnic polarisation and exclusionary nationalism owing to their citizenship status. (Brubaker, 1992).

Discussion

The Indo-Myanmar borderlands are a reflection of shifting strategic discourses and competing logics of state territoriality, geopolitical realism of borderland studies. The northeastern part of India has faced decades of marginalisation from the mainstream discourses; however, the light of the day is visible now for Northeast India. This frontier is positioned as a vital corridor for connectivity, commerce and diplomacy under the frameworks of the Act East Policy and regional infrastructure projects like the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Project.

The reimagining of the Indo-Myanmar borderlands as a zone of connectivity, economic integration, and strategic cooperation remains deeply contested at both local and structural levels. While India's Act East Policy envisions the consequences of securitisation, surveillance and marginalisation rather than development, which is all-inclusive. On the ground, borderland populations frequently negotiate dual loyalties, informal networks, and ethnic affiliations that do not align with national boundaries or strategic infrastructural projects. At the structural level, geopolitical tensions—particularly the influence of China, the instability following the 2021 Myanmar coup, and India's asymmetric border policies have further complicated the region's transformation (Jacob, 2022). Thus, the narratives of development and security promoted by the state often clash with those inhabiting these border spaces, making the region a site of both opportunity and resistance.

Considering the perspective of Borderland theory, borders are not simply demarcated lines of sovereignty but are instead dynamic and negotiated zones of interaction (Donnan and Wilson, 1999; Van Schendel, 2005). The Indo-Myanmar border is characterised by this porosity, overlapping ethnic networks and informal economic flows. Several ethnic communities, such as the Nagas (Konyak tribe), Kukis, Chins and Mizos, whose cultural and familial affiliations transcend the artificial lines drawn during colonial state formation, as visible in the interactions in the border villages in their everyday life. The Westphalian model of rigid territorial control is undermined by this mobility, which can be seen in these border communities. This is a challenge to the state's capacity to exercise uninterrupted sovereignty. There is even the existence of a traditional monarchy system in these border villages on both sides of the border, where the monarch controls more than thirty villages on the Myanmar side and five to seven villages on the Indian side of the border. Territoriality, understood as the attempt to assert control over space to influence people and relationships (Sack, 1986), plays out in complex ways in this region.

The local communities in the border villages of the Indo-Myanmar frontier perceive government initiatives like border fencing and counterinsurgency operations as exclusionary and disempowering. However, there are communities which have accepted the Inner Line Permit (ILP system) as they are sceptical about the movement of outsiders in their land. These spatial strategies introduced by the Indian government have not been accepted; rather, it has deepened the historical sense of alienation and reinforced local resistance to central authority. There were instances when local communities have resisted border security forces in these border regions.

India's engagement with Myanmar from a realist perspective is driven by national security and balance of power considerations. The strategic imperative to counter China's growing footprint in Myanmar, with the help of military cooperation, infrastructure investments like the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Project, and political alignment, has elevated the region's significance in India's foreign policy calculus. Thus, in the Indo-Myanmar borderlands, the state interests override the complexities of local social fabrics in a broader geopolitical context.

The existence of a security-centric realism fails to address the insecurities linked to the citizenship of the ethnic groups inhabiting the borderlands. There are instances where these border

communities have faced precarious legal identities due to historical accounts of migration and undocumented cross-border movements. Citizenship here becomes a site of political turmoil, its definition tied to ethnicity, language and perceived allegiance to nation state and not just legal documentation (Brubaker, 1992). This precariousness is particularly acute in post-conflict or conflict-prone regions where groups displaced by violence may be denied recognition, leading to statelessness or legal invisibility.

The collapse of democratic governance in Myanmar after the 2021 military coup has generated cascading effects along India's northeastern border. As insurgents, refugees, and illicit networks take advantage of the porous and under-governed frontier, India faces the challenge of addressing humanitarian concerns while safeguarding its national security and strategic interests. For instance, the influx of Chin, Kuki and Zo refugees into Mizoram and Manipur has strained local resources and stirred political tensions (Scroll.in, 2023). Simultaneously, armed clashes between the Tatmadaw and ethnic resistance groups near the Sagaing and Chin regions have enabled Indian insurgents like the NSCN-K (YA) and PLA to regroup across the border and exploit weak surveillance zones (International Crisis Group, 2024). Reports also indicate a rise in arms and narcotics trafficking along this corridor, complicating India's border management efforts (The Hindu, 2024).

Strategic Implications

Myanmar's strategic outlook is shaped by the dual imperatives of economic development and internal security. Myanmar is geographically situated at the crossroads of South and Southeast Asia, gaining a leverage to enhance its regional connectivity and expand trade links with key nations in geopolitics, including China, India and ASEAN. Projects such as the Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway and the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project illustrate this vision, aiming to facilitate access to international markets and integrate Myanmar into the regional supply chains. Myanmar's economic links with India—particularly in sectors such as agriculture, textiles, and energy have fostered growing interdependence between the two countries. At the same time, Myanmar's domestic security landscape, marked by long-standing insurgencies in its border regions, most of which are actively working with insurgents from the northeast, poses significant security challenges. There are historical and ideological linkages of many ethnic armed groups operating within Myanmar with insurgent movements in India's Northeast. This has led to collaborative security measures, including coordinated military operations and intelligence exchanges, as both states seek to contain cross-border militancy. Stability in these regions is thus not only critical for Myanmar's national cohesion but also essential to advance its broader economic and strategic objectives (Ministry of Home Affairs, 2022).

India's engagement with Myanmar is shaped by a combination of strategic interests and economic motivations, particularly in response to China's expanding presence in the region. With initiatives such as the China-Myanmar Economic Corridor, Beijing has significantly increased its influence within Myanmar, prompting New Delhi to enhance its own bilateral cooperation as a strategic countermeasure. It is imperative for India to foster stability and collaboration with Myanmar to secure its northeastern borders and reinforce its presence in the Indo-Pacific region. Key infrastructure projects like the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Project and the India-Myanmar-Thailand Trilateral Highway form essential pillars of India's Act East Policy. These initiatives aim to strengthen regional integration and improve connectivity between Northeast India and Southeast Asia, contributing not only to local economic progress but also to India's broader geopolitical objectives in an evolving regional context (ISEAS, 2024).

Myanmar occupies a pivotal position in facilitating the integration of India's Northeast with broader regional trade networks. Cross-border commerce, which particularly involves agricultural produce, textiles, and handicrafts, plays an essential role in supporting local economies on both sides.

However, persistent infrastructural challenges and inadequate regulatory coordination have been a hindrance to the realisation of this economic potential. Enhancing bilateral trade frameworks and investing in efficient logistical systems could significantly boost outcomes for border regions.

Major infrastructure projects such as the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project are central to this effort, aiming to shorten transit routes, enhance trade flows and provide vital market access to landlocked northeastern states. This impetus for growth is needed for improving the regional development of an otherwise economically backwards region (Das, 2024).

The recent surrender of over 200 cadres of the *People's Defence Force-Kalay (PDF-Kalay)* and *People's Defence Force-Kangpokpi (PDF-KK)*—locally known as PKK—to the Myanmar junta in July 2025 marks a significant shift in the regional security dynamics along the India-Myanmar border. This development carries important implications for India's strategic calculations, particularly in its efforts to secure the Indo-Myanmar frontier and foster stability in the Northeast under the broader Act East Policy Framework. The surrender signals a weakening of anti-junta resistance forces in parts of Myanmar's Sagaing and Chin regions, which border India's Northeast, potentially allowing Tatmadaw to consolidate territorial control and increase military presence near Indian borders (International Crisis Group, 2024)

Kaladan Project: A Brief Overview

The Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project (KMMTTP) represents a strategically significant initiative aimed at enhancing connectivity between India's Northeastern region and Myanmar's southwestern coastline. This project aims to shorten the trade route between Kolkata and the Northeast and act as an alternative to the geographically constrained Siliguri Corridor. This would promote logistical efficiency and promote regional trade. The KMMTTP is structured around three core components that form an integrated transport network. The first phase involves the development of Sittwe Port on the Rakhine coast of Myanmar, facilitating maritime transport from Kolkata over a distance of approximately 539 kilometres. This is followed by a 225-kilometre inland waterway linking Sittwe to Setpyitpyin along the Kaladan River. The final component comprises a 62-kilometre road segment extending from Setpyitpyin to the Indo-Myanmar border, where it connects with the existing road network in Mizoram (Hindu).

Figure 1 represents the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project from Sittwe port to India's Kolkata.

Source: "Indian Look East Policy and the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project of Western Burma," *Mizzima*, 24 January 2013

Sittwe Port, situated approximately 250 kilometres from India's northeastern state of Mizoram, functions as a crucial juncture within the Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project (KMMTTP), by integration of maritime and island transport systems to establish a comprehensive transit corridor. This multi-modal infrastructure is designed to facilitate the movement of goods from India's eastern seaboard to its Northeastern states via Myanmar, thereby supporting the objectives of India's Act East Policy. India is changing in this global world order by enhancing regional connectivity and promoting cross-border economic collaborations. This project contributes significantly to India's broader strategic and developmental engagement with Southeast Asia.

The Kaladan Multi-Modal Transit Transport Project (KMMTTP) is aligned with the overarching objectives of India's Act East Policy by serving as a cornerstone in advancing sub-regional connectivity and trade. Beyond the principal transport corridor, complementary initiatives include river dredging, developmental programs in Myanmar's Rakhine State, and the enhancement of road infrastructure linking Kalewa to Aizawl, eventually connecting with the Aizawl-Guwahati National Highway.

These interconnected projects are designed to ensure a seamless transport network, which eventually fosters strong economic linkages between India and Myanmar. Moreover, the successful implementation of the Kaladan project is anticipated to open new avenues for trade, deepen regional integration and reinforce India's strategic presence in Southeast Asia (Vasisht, 2023).

Political Cooperation as a Cornerstone of Bilateral Relations

Among the four principal pillars of bilateral relations, which are political, security, defence and economic, and other forms of cooperation, it has been observed that political cooperation stands out as the most pivotal. It serves as the primary catalyst for India and Myanmar relations. The leadership in both nations has remained steadfast in its commitment to deepening the multi-dimensional engagement, grounded in longstanding historical and cultural connections and guided by the Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence. Myanmar has consistently expressed support for India's growing partnership with the Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN), especially in the context of establishing an ASEAN community by 2015 and providing developmental assistance to CLMV (Cambodia, Lao PDR, Myanmar and Vietnam) countries. India's view of Myanmar as a strategic conduit between South Asia and Southeast Asia has resonated with Myanmar, underpinning their mutual commitment to frameworks like the Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC) and the Mekong-Ganga Cooperation (SAARC), attained in August 2008, which is a reflection of cross-regional connectivity (Bhatia, 2011)

In February 2021, there was a military coup led by Commander-in-Chief Min Aung Hlaing in February 2021 India initially aimed to maintain close links with the military regime in Naypyitaw. Historically, New Delhi has prioritised stable relations with whichever government holds power in Myanmar to safeguard its strategic interests like border security, regional connectivity and balancing China's influence. India has also depended on successive Myanmar governments to assist in its counter-insurgency operations against separatist groups in its northeastern region, many of which have bases of operation across the border. India adjusted its strategy by strengthening relations with opposition groups while maintaining ties with the military regime, including extending humanitarian assistance following the destructive earthquake on 28th March, 2025 (Crisis Group, 2025).

Conclusion

In the current geopolitical scenario, the dynamic evolution of the India-Myanmar relationship holds profound implications for the security, economic development and socio-political landscape of

India's Northeastern region. While joint initiatives in terms of border surveillance and connectivity infrastructure offer strategic advantages, there are persistent challenges like insurgency, irregular migration and Myanmar's political instability, which have been undermining regional stability. This analysis underscores that the post-2021 political upheaval in Myanmar has significantly reshaped the security environment along India's northeastern frontier, resistance from armed groups, displacement and the broader geopolitical contestation between China and India.

The findings suggest that Myanmar's instability acts as a key driver of cross-border threats, thereby necessitating a responsive and adaptive model of border governance that balances national security concerns with a touch of humanitarian obligations. Furthermore, China's deepening political and economic footprint in Myanmar poses urgent security dilemmas for India's strategic interests in the region. These conditions underscore the urgent need for a nuanced diplomatic approach—one that safeguards India's regional aspirations without alienating Naypyidaw. India should also focus on the marginalised border communities, which need to benefit from the development outcomes of the Act East Policy initiatives. This will rule out the shortcomings of historically centralised planning models.

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